

What is your state of mind today?

Please vote! The exploitation strategy is important, in order to :

What kind of support tool would be the most helpful for you to well exploit your results?

Which support on exploitation would you value most?

create business model
additional funding
use canvas
zenodo
reaching stakeholders
zenedo and openaire
training
approach funders
define uvp